

A Comparative Evaluation of Adverse Effects following Immunization with COVAXIN and COVISHIELD among Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Jharkhand

Mona Kumari¹, Kunal Priyadarshi², Rabi Bhushan³

¹Associate Professor and HOD, Dept of Pharmacology, Shaheed Nirmal Mahato Medical College, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

²Tutor, Dept of Pharmacology, Shaheed Nirmal Mahato Medical College, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

³Tutor, Dept of Community Medicine, Shaheed Nirmal Mahato Medical College, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Rajiv Ranjan Das

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Abstract:

Background: Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has led to significant global health and economic impacts. Vaccines such as COVISHIELD and COVAXIN have been approved for emergency use in India to mitigate the pandemic.

Objectives: To evaluate the adverse effect profiles of COVISHIELD and COVAXIN vaccines among healthcare workers in a tertiary care setting.

Methods: An observational prospective cohort study was conducted from April to July 2021 in Jharkhand, India. The study included 590 participants who received two doses of either COVISHIELD or COVAXIN. Data on adverse effects were collected using a structured questionnaire based on WHO guidelines.

Results: Most adverse effects were mild and resolved within 3-7 days. Common side effects included fever, general weakness, headache, myalgia, and injection site pain. While COVAXIN recipients reported more adverse effects than COVISHIELD recipients after both doses, the differences were not statistically significant. The incidence of adverse events decreased with the second dose for both vaccines.

Discussion: The study found no serious adverse events or hospitalizations related to vaccination. The findings are consistent with other studies indicating that both vaccines have an acceptable safety profile. However, limitations include potential reporting bias and the need for long-term surveillance to assess future effects.

Conclusion: Both COVISHIELD and COVAXIN vaccines demonstrated safety and clinical acceptability with mild adverse effects. The study supports continued vaccination efforts but highlights the need for extensive evaluation to assess long-term effects and plan booster dose programs effectively.

Keywords: Covishield, Covaxin, COVID-19, Corona, Virus.

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Introduction

Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19), emerged in China in late 2019 from a zoonotic source. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) was found to be the cause of COVID 19. The majority of Covid-19 cases either are asymptomatic or resulted in only mild disease.

The pandemic not only inflicted mortality and morbidity across the globe but also crippled the economies of most of the nations affected by it. Numerous researches were conducted worldwide to know about the effective management of cases with antipyretics, antivirals, steroids, and other investigational therapies. Also seeing the high infectivity of the virus, social distancing and masks were being promoted to prevent its spread [1]. Vaccines were needed to reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with Covid-19, and multiple

platforms at different levels have been involved in the rapid development of vaccines across the globe [2]. In India, the Drugs Controller General of India (DCGI) approved two COVID-19 vaccines- Covishield and Covaxin for restricted emergency use on January 3, 2021[3]. The vaccination drive started actively in India on January 16, 2021 with the two vaccines and later Sputnik-V, another COVID-19 vaccine, marketed by Dr Reddy's Laboratories, was granted approval.

As per the results of 3rd phase clinical trials released on July 3rd 2021, the vaccines exhibited an efficacy of 81% and 90% for COVISHIELD and COVAXIN respectively [4]. Bharat Biotech and Serum Institute of India, the companies that market Covaxin and Covishield respectively released fact sheets of the vaccines to provide information for

the healthcare workers and vaccine recipients. As the vaccines were granted fast track approval, limited data was available on the efficacy and the safety of vaccines at the time of approval. The most common side effects experienced after both the vaccines were pain redness at injection site, mild fever, headache joint pain, and muscle pain [5]. Various studies were done to study the safety of these two vaccines. Several studies have been carried out during post market analysis for better understanding of the side effects of the vaccines. The current study was carried out to evaluate the adverse effect profiles of both COVISHIELD and COVAXIN separately with focus on severity and duration of the side effects among the participants. In addition, the differences in adverse reactions of the first and second dose within and between these vaccines was also analysed.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: An observational prospective cohort study was carried out in a tertiary care teaching hospital, located in the State of Jharkhand, India from April to July, 2021. Recipients who had two doses of either COVISHIELD or COVAXIN were included in the study. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before start of the study. A questionnaire based on WHO guidelines was prepared to collect the data regarding the side effects following the first and second dose of vaccination [6]. The study was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Sample Size: All the adults above the age of 18 yrs attending the health center for vaccination against SARS-CoV during the period of 1st April 2021 to 31st July 2021 were included in the study. The list of people who were vaccinated was collected from the Institutional database of COVID-19 vaccination.

Inclusion Criteria: Subjects who received two doses of either COVISHIELD or COVAXIN vaccine were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Subjects who did not complete two doses of vaccine, history of past or present COVID-19 infection and those not willing to give informed consent were excluded from the study.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a structured questionnaire which was translated into the local language. The questionnaire contained the details of vaccine type, adverse effects, duration of onset and demographic data. Semi open type of questions about the adverse reactions was mentioned so that the participants could add any adverse event (AE) they had experienced, other than those mentioned in the list. Measures were taken to handle the post vaccination adverse effects including hospitalization.

Data Analysis: After the data collection, it was cleaned and statistically analysed using SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA. All the data were subjected to descriptive analysis while associations were calculated using Chi-square test. All inferential tests were carried out using a confidence interval of 95% and significance level of 0.05.

Results

Out of 640 people with whom the study was started 10 were lost to follow-up and 40 did not develop any adverse effect following both the doses of vaccine. The study was continued with 590 participants out of which 380 had taken COVAXIN and 210 took COVISHIELD. Time of onset of adverse event was assessed with respect to first and second dose of both vaccines. The adverse effects were mostly mild and none of the participants required hospitalization. No death was reported during the study period. No beneficiary reported any adverse event during the observation period i.e. 30 minutes following vaccination. No anaphylactic reaction was reported among the beneficiaries. For both the vaccines (Covishield and covaxin) and for both the doses, maximum participation was shown by males (76%) and those belonging to age groups 30-50 years (55%). A statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) was found between ages and reporting of adverse events with 66% participants in the age group of 30-50 years experiencing adverse events. It was observed that most participants who came for vaccination were educated upto class 12th (45%) while 35% were graduates and only 20% had done post-graduation. Majority of the participants in both the groups were residents of urban area. Almost 94% practiced Hinduism. The proportion of participants who experienced adverse effects within 24 hrs after the first dose was not significantly high in Covaxin group (40%) when compared to (38%) in Covishield group ($p = 0.943$, chi-square test.). A rise in proportion (42%) was seen in COVISHIELD group during 24-72 hrs period after 1st dose which was not significant. Similar pattern was observed after 2nd dose with COVAXIN showing higher proportion of adverse events (38%) compared to COVISHIELD group within 24 hrs. More than 80% of the adverse effects occurred within 3 days after the first and second dose in both groups and the graphical representation of the time of onset of adverse effects is shown in Figure no. 2 and 3

As shown in Table 1&2, the highest reported symptom in the first dose for covaxin was fever (58%) followed by general weakness (47%) and for covishield it was myalgia (67%) and weakness (57%). While in the second dose, the maximum reported symptom for covaxin was headache (24%) and for covishield it was myalgia again (45%). The results were statistically significant with $p < 0.0001$.

The local adverse reaction observed commonly in COVAXIN group was joint pain (24%) as compared to injection site pain and tenderness (47%) as seen in COVISHIELD group. The incidence of adverse events declined with the second dose when compared to the first dose both

with Covishield and Covaxin with some symptoms showing significant ($p < 0.001$) reduction as shown in table.

Interestingly only 1% cases in COVAXIN group and 5-6% cases in COVISHIELD group had rashes/urticaria.

Table 1: Statistical analysis for Covaxin 1st and 2nd dose N= 380

Adverse Effect		COVAXIN		Chi square	P value
		1 st dose N (%)	2 nd dose N (%)		
General weakness	Present	180 (47)	70 (18)	72.16	< 0.0001 s
	absent	200 (53)	310 (82)		
Fever	Present	220 (58)	80 (21)	106	< 0.0001 s
	Absent	160 (42)	300 (79)		
Headache	Present	165 (43)	90 (24)	33.19	< 0.0001 s
	Absent	215 (47)	290 (76)		
Fatigue	Present	60 (16)	35 (09)	7.51	< 0.001 s
	Absent	320(84)	345 (91)		
Myalgia	Present	40 (11)	30 (08)	1.57	0.20 NS
	Absent	340 (89)	350 (92)		
Joint pain	Present	90 (24)	45 (12)	18.24	< 0.0001 s
	Absent	290(76)	335 (88)		
Nausea/ vomiting	Present	30 (08)	20 (05)	2.14	0.143 ns
	Absent	350(92)	360(95)		
Injection site pain/redness/lump	Present	27 (07)	15 (04)	3.62	0.068 ns
	Absent	353(93)	365(96)		
Rashes/Itching	Present	5 (01)	3 (01)	0.51	0.474 ns
	Absent	375(99)	377(99)		
Abdominal pain/Diarrhea	Present	12 (03)	3 (01)	5.27	0.021 ns
	Absent	368(97)	377(99)		

Table 2: Statistical analysis of Covishield 1st and 2nd dose N=210

Adverse Effect		COVISHIELD		Chi square	P value
		1 st dose N (%)	2 nd dose N (%)		
General weakness	Present	120 (57)	80 (38)	15.27	< 0.0001 s
	absent	90 (43)	130(62)		
Fever	Present	110(52)	75 (36)	11.83	< 0.0006 s
	Absent	100(48)	135(64)		
Headache	Present	40 (19)	35 (17)	0.406	0.524 NS
	Absent	170 (81)	175 (83)		
Fatigue	Present	60 (29)	45 (21)	2.85	0.091 Ns
	Absent	150(71)	165(79)		
Myalgia	Present	140(67)	95 (45)	19.57	< 0.001 S
	Absent	70 (33)	115(55)		
Joint pain	Present	55 (26)	45 (21)	1.312	< 0.252 N s
	Absent	155(74)	165(79)		
Nausea/ vomiting	Present	70 (33)	50 (24)	4.66	0.030 ns
	Absent	140(67)	160(76)		
Injection site pain/redness/lump	Present	98 (47)	68 (32)	7.78	0.005 s
	Absent	112(53)	142(68)		
Rashes/Itching	Present	10 (05)	13 (06)	0.41	0.519 ns
	Absent	200(95)	197(94)		
Abdominal pain/Diarrhoea	Present	25 (12)	30 (14)	0.52	0.470 ns
	Absent	185(88)	180(86)		

Figure 1: Distribution of recipients according to Profession

Figure 2: Percentage of subjects developing adverse effects following 1st dose of COVAXIN and COVISHIELD at various time intervals

Figure 3: Percentage of subjects developing adverse effects following 2nd dose of COVAXIN and COVISHIELD at various time intervals

Figure 4: Demographic profile of vaccine recipients (M-Male, F-Female, D- Doctor, N & Pm- Nurse and Paramedics, O- Others)

Discussion

The present study has explored the adverse effect following immunization among the health care workers following the first and second dose of COVAXIN and COVISHIELD vaccination in the middle of the pandemic in the context of tertiary care teaching hospital in Jharkhand. Vaccines have been available for the prophylaxis of COVID-19, its hesitancy in public poses a major challenge in effective implementation of immunization programme [7]. There were no serious adverse effects requiring hospital admission. Anaphylaxis and deaths were not observed. Maximum participation was shown by males (76%) and those belonging to age groups 30–50 years (55%). On the contrary, study done by Mittal et al. in India reported that out of their 532 study participants most of the respondents were between 18-30 years of age [8].

In our study 90% of the recipients developed one or the other adverse effect following vaccination. This was in contrast to a survey conducted in India wherein 66% had reported at least one adverse effect after vaccination [9]. A study done by Klugar et al. in Germany reported that 88.1% of the German health care workers reported at least one side effect following vaccination against COVID-19 [10]. Variation in the percentage could be attributed to our active surveillance wherein repeated enquiring for adverse effects was made. Moreover, this study was carried for a longer period of time. Hence, we could trace for adverse events for more period. The present study observed the significant side effects such as fever (58%),

general weakness (47%) and headache (43%) in COVAXIN recipients which was in contrast to study done by Polack et al which reported fatigue and headache as the most common adverse effects in recipients of COVAXIN [11]. The findings of this study are almost in consonance to the study done by Koyagura et al where the Covaxin beneficiaries too reported fever, headache and body ache as the most frequent ADRs [12].

In the current study the most frequently reported adverse reactions among COVISHIELD beneficiaries were myalgia (67%), weakness (57%) and fever (52%). Almost (47%) of subjects reported tenderness at the injection site. A similar trend was observed in a study done by Radhakrishnan et al which reported tiredness, body ache, and fever and injection site pain as adverse effects reported by maximum number of COVISHIELD recipients [13]. A similar trend in adverse effects was reported by Zhu et al in a study conducted in 2020 wherein myalgia, weakness and fever were the most commonly reported adverse effects following COVISHIELD vaccination [14].

In this study maximum number (80%) of adverse effects were seen within 72 hrs of vaccination for both the vaccines. This was in line with study done by Kamal et al wherein majority of adverse events were noted within the first 48 hrs of vaccination after first and second doses [15]. A similar trend was observed in a study done by Radhakrishnan et al in which about 80% of the adverse events occurred within 3 days after vaccination. In this study it was observed that the adverse events were more in number with Covaxin group as compared

to Covishield group after the first dose. The trend was similar after second dose. There was a slight increase in percentage of recipients having adverse effects following first dose in Covishield group in 24-72 hrs time frame but it was not significant. There was no significant difference observed between Covishield and Covaxin after both the doses when AE data were statistically compared. The results were in consonance with study done by Mittal et al and Koyagura et al wherein Covaxin recipients showed a greater number of adverse effects compared to Covishield group.

The incidence of adverse events declined with the second dose when compared to the first dose for both the groups of recipients. This trend of having of having fewer AEs with the second dose has been observed in a study done in Korea by Jeon et al which showed a significant decline in adverse effects with second dose of vaccine when compared to first dose [16]. On the contrary, a study conducted in a different ethnic population by Lee et al observed more adverse reactions with second dose when compared to first dose [17]. Inbaraj et al observed a similar trend in their study with Covaxin and mRNA COVID vaccines, where the second dose was associated with more AEs compared to the first dose [18]. This could be attributed to the immune response induced by first dose producing virus specific antibodies against the antigens when the second dose of vaccine is given, the memory T cells and B cells would produce a strong immune response and hence the reactogenicity might be more with the second dose compared to first dose. Though the adverse events were more in number with COVAXIN as compared to COVISHIELD after both the doses, all of them were minor in nature. Both vaccines have similar clinical acceptability and safety profile.

Limitations

- The limitation of the study is that optimal sample size to assess the adverse effects was not reached. Results of the study might not be a true representation of the incidence of adverse events and studies with larger sample size are required to generalize the results to the general population.
- The study was conducted only on health care workers hence reporting bias could be possible as reporting of adverse events might be different from the general population.
- Few adverse events could have been coincidental and may not be attributed to the vaccination directly as the period of surveillance was long.
- In this study only short-term adverse effects were evaluated. This highlights the need for long-term surveillance in the general population to evaluate possible future effect of the vaccines.

Conclusion

This study puts forth the short-term adverse events of both the doses the vaccines after two doses. All the symptoms were mild in severity and resolved within 3-7 days. No serious adverse events attributable to vaccines were reported.

The frequency and duration of adverse events were almost similar in both the vaccines. Although the adverse effects were more with Covaxin when compared to Covishield, the difference was not found to be significant.

Our study showed that both the vaccines were safe and have an acceptable safety profile. This study advocates the need for an extensive evaluation to assess the long-term effects of the vaccines for effective planning and implementation of booster dose programme for complete eradication of the disease, as vaccination still remains the most important strategy to fight any future upsurge of the pandemic.

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